

Article

Exergy-Based Evaluation of Ecodesign Strategies for Recyclable and Disassemblable Plastic Components in Automotive Applications

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Abstract

The automotive sector is the third-largest consumer of plastics in Europe, after packaging and construction, and its demand is expected to grow. Plastic recycling at the end of vehicle life remains low, with 80% of plastics ending up in energy recovery or landfills. Three vehicle models (SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV and SEAT Leon Gen. II and III) with two trim versions (Reference and Formula Racing) were examined to identify the most critical plastic components from an exergy perspective. Ecodesign measures were defined by considering both the disassemblability of vehicle components and their recyclability potential as key criteria to evaluate end-of-life recovery pathways and guide material and design optimization strategies. The proposed methodology classified the measures into three types: (1) substitution of high-exergy plastics with lower-impact alternatives; (2) use of recycled plastics instead of primary materials, with substitution rates depending on the material; and (3) reuse of components in new models, evaluated by disassemblability and end-of-life condition. Results show that Type 1 measures achieved savings up to 70 MJ, mainly in the floor covering and engine compartment insulator, while Type 2 measures provided larger reductions, up to 1.7 GJ, mainly in bumpers and carpets. Type 3 measures showed reuse potential for paddings and insulators but faced limitations in carpets and dashboards. Findings highlight the importance of material selection and implementing disassembly and recycling strategies to reduce the exergy of vehicle plastics.

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1. Introduction

The automobile manufacturing sector is one of the most demanding in terms of raw materials [1]. Millions of cars are sold each year, and this number is expected to grow, reaching a global vehicle fleet of nearly 1.5 billion cars worldwide by 2050 [2]. Also, changes in vehicle composition are occurring as a result of the sector's evolution toward safer and

less polluting vehicles [3,4]. Moreover, this evolution is mandatory, as by 2035, all vehicles sold in Europe will be required to have zero emissions [5]. These major transformations in the automotive industry will also lead to a large number of vehicles reaching the end of their life. In Europe, for example, around 10 million vehicles are decommissioned each year [6]. The end-of-life of such a large number of vehicles requires their management by authorized treatment facilities and recycling plants to comply with the reuse, recycling and recovery targets established by Directive 2000/53/EC on end-of-life vehicles [7]. Nevertheless, although these targets are formally met in many Member States with this legislation, between 7 and 9 million tons of waste are generated annually during the treatment of end-of-life vehicles [8]. This indicates that compliance with regulatory targets does not necessarily translate into an effective minimization of residual waste streams, highlighting structural limitations in current recycling and recovery practices. Consequently, there is a need for more comprehensive assessment approaches that go beyond regulatory compliance indicators in order to better identify inefficiencies and opportunities for improvement in end-of-life vehicle management. This legislation sets binding quantitative targets aimed at minimizing the environmental impact of vehicle waste and promoting material recovery within a circular economy framework.

Plastics and microplastics are one of the main sources of pollution because they persist in the environment, can release toxic substances, and accumulate in soils and water, making their impact longer-lasting than that of metals or vehicle fluids [9], and their recycling at the end of a vehicle's life is not as efficient as in the case of metals. For example, it is estimated that approximately 150 kg of plastic waste are generated per end-of-life vehicle recycled [10]. Although technologies for the treatment of automotive shredder residue (ASR) generated during vehicle recycling currently exist, their application is still limited in Europe, and there is still a high potential for improvement [11]. One of the main challenges in recovering plastics from ASR is its inherent heterogeneity, as the concentration of plastics in ASR can vary from 14% to 43% [12]. In addition, the wide diversity of plastics and polymers that constituting this ASR fraction further complicates the recovery process.

An average vehicle contains around 40 different types of plastics, which must be separated in order to be reused in specific applications [13]. The main polymers used in the automotive industry include thermoplastics such as PP, PE, PVC, ABS, PA and PC, as well as polymer blends (e.g., PP-EPDM, ABS-PC and PC-PBT), thermoset composites and elastomers.

Beyond the application of technologies for ASR treatment, another option to improve plastic recycling is to reduce the ASR fraction itself [14]. This requires applying pre-treatment operations that separate plastics before shredding. Measures such as dismantling bumpers, fuel tanks, wheels, and seats prior to shredding have the potential to reduce by up to 42% the mass of ASR landfilled [15]. However, in order to implement these pre-treatment operations, a prior characterization of all plastic components must be carried out to focus on the most critical ones. The application of pre-treatment operations to the most critical automotive components with the aim of improving their recyclability has already been proposed in previous studies [16–20]. These works focused on the classification of components according to thermodynamic parameters related to exergy, using second-law-based indicators to quantify the energy required to transform raw materials into usable components [21].

Embodied exergy can be used as a physical indicator to evaluate the energy required to convert raw materials into manufacturing-ready components. Its application in the automotive sector [22,23] allows the identification of the most critical components in terms of their materials contents, particularly plastic components, which are highly relevant for defining recycling and pre-treatment strategies. Although embodied exergy has also been

applied to electrical and electronic components, often in relation to material rarity, the focus here is on plastic components.

Components with high embodied exergy require large amounts of energy for their production, which not only increases their environmental impact but also highlights the need to prioritize these components in recycling and material optimization strategies. In this context, the recycling and recovery targets established by the Directive 2000/53/EC on end-of-life vehicles promote material recovery based primarily on mass-based indicators [24]. However, such mass-based targets may not fully capture the thermodynamic value of materials, particularly in the case of plastic components with higher embodied exergy. As a result, despite compliance with current regulatory requirements, these components may not be effectively prioritized in end-of-life vehicle management strategies, revealing limitations in existing policy frameworks.

As an example, if the exergy savings for the front bumper of the Ibiza Gen. IV Reference trim is 48.72 MJ in the proposed scenario, under this directive the effective savings would be reduced to approximately 12.18 MJ. This result highlights that compliance with mass-based targets does not necessarily lead to optimal exergy performance.

In addition, economic value (cost/price) can also play an important role in prioritization decisions, as components with higher market value or higher substitution cost may be more attractive for recovery and recycling, even if their mass contribution is limited. In general, components containing engineering polymers (e.g., polyurethanes in foams, polyamides, or polycarbonates) tend to exhibit higher added value compared to commodity polymers such as PP and PE, which may increase their relevance in recovery and recycling strategies [25].

Nevertheless, this aspect is not explicitly incorporated into current regulatory schemes. Moreover, in the case of plastics, economic balances are not a reliable reference, since empirical evidence shows that petrochemical and plastic prices exhibit significant volatility and strong spillover effects across the supply chain [26], which are largely driven by market dynamics rather than intrinsic physical or thermodynamic properties. This further highlights the need for more physically grounded assessment frameworks.

Similarly, Alcoceba-Pascual et al. [27] found that selective recovery of precious metals from electronic parts can lower cumulative exergy demand by up to 20%. Compared to plastics, metals offer higher specific exergy savings per kilogram but require purer fractions and more complex metallurgical routes. Therefore, improving material selection and minimizing the use of plastics with high embodied exergy during material production are key aspects for maximizing overall exergy efficiency in the automotive industry.

In addition to material selection and recycling strategies, design-for-disassembly approaches have been widely applied to assess the feasibility of component recovery at the end of life. These approaches typically rely on operational criteria such as accessibility, disassembly time, tool requirements, and handling complexity to evaluate the effort associated with component removal [28,29]. In the context of end-of-life vehicles, such parameters have been identified as key factors influencing the efficiency of material recovery processes [30]. Therefore, assessing disassembly feasibility constitutes a relevant complementary perspective when analyzing potential strategies to improve resource efficiency in automotive systems.

The main objective of this work is to evaluate the exergy of plastic vehicle parts and identify the most critical ones in terms of their physical exergy value. This is done in order to propose eco-design measures to increase the sustainability of the plastics used in vehicles from an exergy perspective.

By applying a methodology that considers disassemblability and recyclability, this study proposes strategies to reduce the embodied exergy in these components. The results

indicate that substituting high-exergy plastics with lower-impact alternatives can yield savings up to 70 MJ, while the use of recycled plastics provides even larger reductions, up to 1.7 GJ. Furthermore, the reuse of certain components shows potential benefits, although limitations exist for specific parts such as carpets and dashboards. Overall, the results underscore the importance of material selection, disassembly, and recycling strategies in improving the sustainability and exergy efficiency of plastic components of vehicles.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Exergy as a Thermodynamic Basis for Resource Assessment

Conventional approaches used in waste management and recycling policies, including those defined under the Directive 2000/53/EC on end-of-life vehicles, are predominantly based on mass indicators, such as recycling or recovery rates, which quantify the amount of material recovered at the end of a product's life [31], typically expressed in mass terms, measured in kilograms. Although these indicators are useful for tracking material flows, several authors have highlighted that mass-based criteria fail to reflect differences in resource scarcity, production complexity, or environmental relevance of materials [32,33]. This limitation is especially relevant for complex products like vehicles, where small amounts of certain materials may involve disproportionately high resource use. Recycling strategies based only on mass can therefore overlook critical materials [4].

Exergy, as a thermodynamic parameter, measures the maximum useful work obtainable from a system relative to a reference environment. Unlike mass, it accounts for both the quantity and quality of energy and materials, and is irreversibly lost in real processes due to entropy generation [34,35]. Expressing materials and processes in terms of exergy allows for the evaluation of resource quality degradation throughout a product's life cycle and helps identify stages where valuable resources are lost, making it a more effective indicator for sustainability assessments and eco-design compared to analyses based solely on mass [36].

Differences in embodied exergy among polymers arise mainly from variations in feedstock origin, process complexity, and the number of energy-intensive transformation steps involved [37]. In particular, polymers produced from several petroleum-based chemicals, such as styrene-butadiene rubber (SBR), exhibit higher embodied exergy values due to their more complex production routes, which include additional cracking, separation, and purification stages [38]. For instance, plastics as polyethylene (PE) and polypropylene (PP) have embodied exergy values of $24.3 \text{ MJ}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$ and $39.0 \text{ MJ}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$, respectively, whereas more complex polymers like polyamide 6.6 (PA6.6) and SBR reach $59.3 \text{ MJ}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$ and $73.0 \text{ MJ}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$, respectively, as reported in Table 1.

Table 1. Polymers analyzed and quantified in terms of their embodied exergy. Own elaboration based on [39–45].

Polymer	Embodied Exergy $\text{MJ}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$
PP	39.0
PE	24.3
PVC	25.5
ABS	69.8
PU	41.0
PA6.6	59.3
PET	51.2
SBR	73.0
EPDM	55.9
EPM	32.3

Furthermore, although a significant contribution to the total exergy of fossil-based polymers generally originates from the upstream production of naphtha, encompassing crude oil extraction, refining, and subsequent conversion processes, each associated with substantial thermodynamic irreversibilities [46], this contribution is excluded from the present analysis as it is common to all fossil-based polymers and therefore does not allow for a meaningful differentiation among materials.

Chemical exergy associated with the higher heating value (HHV) of polymers represents the intrinsic energy content of the fossil resource from which the material is derived. For most fossil-based polymers composed primarily of carbon and hydrogen (e.g., PE, PP, PS), HHVs are relatively similar, typically ranging between 40 and 47 MJ/kg [47,48]. Consequently, this contribution can be considered approximately constant across the materials analyzed and is not influenced by the industrial transformation stages. Including this term would introduce a dominant and nearly constant contribution to the total exergy, limiting the ability to distinguish differences between materials and potentially masking the effects associated with processing and manufacturing stages.

It is worth noting that accounting for HHV would be relevant in scenarios where plastics are intended for energy recovery (e.g., through incineration), as it reflects their potential as fuels; however, from a circular economy perspective, this option should be considered a last resort, after strategies such as reduction, reuse, and recycling have been exhausted.

Since the objective of this study is to evaluate and compare the embodied exergy linked to industrial transformation processes, the intrinsic chemical exergy of the fossil feedstock is excluded. This approach enables a more meaningful differentiation among polymers and provides more relevant insights for material selection and design.

For plastics, which are mainly derived from fossil resources, this thermodynamic perspective is commonly applied through the concept of embodied exergy, defined as the cumulative exergy required for production from primary resources. Embodied exergy provides a consistent basis for comparing polymers and end-of-life strategies beyond mass-based criteria. It is calculated as the sum of the exergies of all stages required for their production: (1) polymer manufacturing, (2) hydrocarbon production from naphtha, (3) naphtha production from fossil fuels, and (4) fossil fuels extraction from the environment [46].

2.2. Vehicle Models

Within this research, three SEAT vehicle models were analyzed: SEAT Ibiza Generation IV (Gen. IV) and SEAT Leon Generations II and III (Gen. II and III). The selection criteria included the models' contribution to total brand sales, variations in equipment levels, and differences in model versions relative to their market age. As shown in Table 2, the data reflect SEAT's global sales of new vehicles to its dealer network.

Table 2. Sales trends for the SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV and SEAT Leon Gen. II and III models in 2022, 2023, and 2024 [49,50].

Model	Units	2022		2023		2024	
		Based on SEAT's Total Sales	Units	Based on SEAT Models Total Sales	Units	Based on SEAT Models Total Sales	Units
SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV	56,400	24.1%	72,700	26.2%	106,900	36.2%	
SEAT Leon Gen. II and III	35,300	15.1%	39,700	14.3%	41,300	14.0%	

From the equipment-level perspective, the Reference and Formula Racing trims have been considered. The choice of these trims is due to the fact that they represent the lowest and highest equipment levels of each SEAT model, respectively. The main differences between the Formula Racing trim compared to the Reference trim are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Exclusive equipment of the Formula Racing version compared to the Reference model.

Interior	Exterior
Sports seats	Chrome on exhaust tip
Multifunction steering wheel	Sporty bumpers, side skirts, and rear spoiler
Dual-zone climate control	Tinted windows
Cruise control	Electrically adjustable and heated exterior mirrors
Power windows on all doors	Parking sensors
—	LED lights

2.3. Methodological Steps

The recyclability and disassemblability of the critical components of the vehicles models under study were analyzed to identify the most impactful eco-design measures. The measures obtained provide a basis for the environmental optimization of the design. Subsequently, the savings resulting from their implementation were evaluated in terms of exergy, which allowed the real impact of the eco-design strategies to be quantified from a thermodynamic perspective and provided a more comprehensive view of their feasibility and benefits.

Figure 1a shows a structured and progressive approach to the steps followed to carry out the study, from the characterization of materials to the quantification of the impact of the improvements implemented after a comprehensive evaluation of vehicle eco-design. This workflow reflects the relationship between the different stages, clarifies the procedure followed, and highlights the continuity between the identification of critical components, their analysis from the perspectives of recyclability and disassemblability, and the exergy evaluation of the proposed improvements. Moreover, this structured approach ensures that each stage builds on the previous one, enabling a consistent and systematic identification of the most critical components and supporting a robust evaluation of eco-design strategies.

The tasks performed in Step 1 are summarized in Figure 1b, outlining the main activities and goals of this initial stage. The process began with compiling a complete inventory of all vehicle parts (1). This inventory was provided by SEAT S.A. (Martorell, Barcelona, Spain) based on a bill of materials for each car configuration detailing all parts, components, and raw materials required to manufacture the product, in this case the different parts of the analyzed vehicle models. From this information, the total weight of each part and its subcomponents was calculated. However, for some parts, the total weight was not available; in such cases, it was determined by summing the weights of all subcomponents (2). Finally, the plastic mass of each part and of the vehicle as a whole was determined (3). Further details on these data processing steps, including the identification and correction of inconsistencies arising from duplicated subcomponents, are provided in the Supplementary Materials, in the section titled “Methodological steps”.

Since in some cases subparts appeared with a more specific plastic designation (for example, a PA part could be listed as PA6 or PA66), it was necessary to standardize the nomenclature so that the main plastic was used in such cases (6). Due to the extensive variety of plastics used in vehicles, a systematic classification was performed to group them into distinct families, including thermoplastics, thermosets, elastomers, and other types. The outcomes of this harmonization for each category are detailed in Table 4.

Figure 1. (a) Overview of the applied methodology, from critical part identification through to eco-design impact evaluation. (b) Workflow illustrating the sequence of tasks comprising Step 1, from the initial data provided by SEAT to the harmonization of plastics and the final classification of parts. ^a Reference trims. ^b Formula Racing trims.

Table 4. Classification of Thermoplastic and Thermoset Polymers, Elastomeric Polymers and others.

Denomination	Abbreviation	Denomination	Abbreviation
Thermoplastic and Thermoset Polymers			
Polyethylene	PE	Polycarbonate	PC
Polypropylene	PP	Polyphenylene sulfide	PPS
Acrylonitrile butadiene styrene	ABS	Polysulfones	PSU
Polyvinyl chloride	PVC	Polymethyl methacrylate	PMMA
Polyethylene terephthalate	PET	Polyoxymethylene (Polyacetal)	POM
Polyamide	PA	Ethylene-vinyl alcohol	EVOH
Polyurethane	PU	Polyvinyl butyral	PVB
Polystyrene	PS	Polypropylene–ethylene blend	E/P
Elastomeric Polymers			
Styrene-butadiene rubber	SBR	Epichlorohydrin rubber	ECO
Natural rubber	NR	Acrylic rubber	ACM
Ethylene propylene diene monomer	EPDM	Silicone rubber	VMQ
Fluoroelastomer	FKM	—	—

Table 4. Cont.

Denomination	Abbreviation	Denomination	Abbreviation
Others			
Thermoplastic elastomers	TPS-SEBS	Phenolic resin	PF
Acrylate ethylene monomer rubber	AEM	Butyl rubber	IIR
Copolyester	TPC-ET	—	—

Once the data were processed, filters were applied by plastic type and by part (7). Subsequently, the parts were classified according to their contribution to the total plastic demand and according to the proportion of plastics relative to their total mass. This latter analysis made it possible to group the vehicle parts both by plastic type and by their contribution to the overall plastic demand of the vehicle.

The second step of the methodology is the identification of the most critical parts. These are defined in the study models by the type of plastics used and their associated exergy. A deeper dive into the polymers considered in this study and their production routes can be observed in Supplementary Materials Table S1.

This classification framework allows moving beyond a purely descriptive characterization by explicitly linking part-level plastic distributions to material criticality and exergy demand, enabling a more analytical interpretation of plastic demand patterns across vehicle components.

2.3.1. Calculation of the Criticality of Plastic Parts in Terms of Embodied Exergy

According to the polymer characterization described above and the previously determined embodied exergy values, the exergy for each vehicle component is calculated. In this study, exergy is evaluated for all parts with a plastic mass of at least 1 kg and a plastic content of at least 80% of the total mass.

In order to identify the most relevant components for the analysis, a screening threshold of plastic mass ≥ 1 kg and plastic content $\geq 80\%$ was applied. This criterion was defined to focus on large and predominantly plastic components that contribute most significantly to the total plastic mass of the vehicle.

This selection is supported by previous studies [19], which analyzed vehicles across different segments, model years, and equipment levels, showing that a substantial proportion of the total plastic mass is concentrated in heavier components with high plastic content. In contrast, smaller components, although numerous, contribute marginally to the overall material mass and embodied exergy.

From a methodological perspective, the threshold is based on a research-oriented rationale aimed at capturing components that are most relevant for material comparison, recycling strategies, and circular design. By prioritizing high-mass and high-plastic-content parts, the analysis targets elements with the greatest potential impact, while avoiding unnecessary complexity associated with low-impact components.

Using this characterization and the EE values listed in Table 4, the embodied exergy for each component is determined according to the following equation:

$$EE_{Base\ Case} = \sum_{i=1}^n EE_i \left[\frac{MJ}{kg} \right] \cdot m_i [kg] \quad (1)$$

where $EE_{Base\ Case}$ is the embodied exergy of plastics for each vehicle model (base case), m_i is the mass of each polymer comprising the piece and EE_i is the embodied exergy of each

polymer comprising the piece. The most critical components are listed in Table 5. These were selected based on their frequency of occurrence across all analyzed models and are ranked by exergy from highest to lowest.

Table 5. Critical Part Families for Recyclability Analysis.

Part Designation	Part Family
Front seat foam (backrest)	Foams and padding
Door panel storage compartment	Housings and panels
Rear seat foam (cushion)	Foams and padding
Rear seat foam (backrest)	Foams and padding
Front end module	Structure
Front window guide	Guides
Engine compartment insulator	Insulators
Front door panel	Housings and panels
Rear door panel	Housings and panels
Front bumper	Exterior element
Rear bumper	Exterior element
Dashboard	Dashboard
Fuel tank	Tanks
Floor covering	Upholstery

High embodied exergy values indicate that a significant amount of exergy is required to produce a vehicle part, reflecting both the material content and the complexity of its manufacturing processes. For example, front and rear seat foams (backrest and cushion) have some of the highest embodied exergy among plastics vehicle parts. Identifying parts with high embodied exergy enables more effective allocation of recycling efforts and supports design and material optimization to reduce the overall exergy demand of automotive manufacturing.

2.3.2. Disassemblability Analysis

The disassemblability of each component was investigated for all the vehicle models considered in the project. The third step consisted of analyzing the disassemblability of the critical parts of the vehicle models under study.

This process was carried out in collaboration with the Vehicle Research Institute, Centro Zaragoza S.A (CZ), which comprises 17 insurance companies and aims to improve road safety and vehicle reparability. Audatex (AudaPlus/AudaTaller–online platform) database, a tool widely employed by insurance companies, automotive repair shops, and claims services to estimate repair costs and manage insurance claims, was used.

Audatex (AudaPlus/AudaTaller–online platform) relies on an extensive database containing detailed information on a wide range of vehicles, including models, years of manufacture, spare parts, labor costs, and recommended repair procedures [51]. The database is regularly updated to reflect changes in the automotive industry, such as new technologies, materials, and repair techniques. The software generates a report that includes the disassembly times for the parts as well as the operations to be performed. Differences in disassemblability between models were also taken into account, as the removal of the same component may require different procedures or effort depending on the vehicle model.

2.3.3. Recyclability Assessment of Critical Plastic Parts

In the fourth step, the recyclability of the most critical components was analyzed. It was found that the differences in composition between similar components, both within the same model and across different models, were minimal. For example, the foam of the seat cushion and backrest, the front and rear door panels, the front and rear bumpers, and the

dashboard in different trims all exhibit very similar compositions. Consequently, components were grouped into families, and recyclability was studied for a single representative model from each family (see Table 5 for details).

Based on this grouping, a representative component from each family was studied for the SEAT Leon Gen. III Formula Racing model. This vehicle was selected as an example because complete information on its composition was available, unlike for other models, and as it also reflects the materials and techniques currently used in the automotive industry.

2.3.4. Factors Influencing Recyclability

The recyclability of plastics used in the automotive sector is primarily determined by the nature of the polymer. In some cases, certain polymers cannot be recycled; in others, industrial-scale processes have not yet been developed, and in some instances, recycling can significantly degrade material properties.

Therefore, one key aspect to consider for improving polymer recycling is polymer compatibility. Modern vehicles contain between 20 and 40 types of polymers, many of which are incompatible during recycling. Mixing incompatible plastics produces materials with degraded properties that cannot be reused in their original application, and tolerance to such mixtures is usually below 2% [19]. This issue is further exacerbated by the use of components made from more than one type of plastic for aesthetic purposes, such as surface coatings or films that provide specific finishes.

Moreover, the use of additives and fillers, incorporated to enhance mechanical properties, fire resistance, or modify color, can also complicate recycling [52]. These additives may contain heavy metals or halogens, hinder the separation of glass or natural fibers from the polymer, and, due to the lack of information on their composition, make it difficult to classify plastics and select the appropriate recycling method. The wide variety of possible additives and combinations results in highly variable material composition, requiring experimental studies to determine material degradation and potential reuse in different applications.

Considering the challenges associated with material composition and disassembly, ensuring the economic feasibility of recycling requires high volumes of material with a supply that is stable over time, and that the costs of disassembly are offset by the revenues obtained from the sale or reuse of the recovered plastics.

Economic feasibility is directly influenced by factors such as the number of polymers and subcomponents, material compatibility, and the presence of mechanical or adhesive connections between parts. Having detailed information on these aspects, together with the analysis of the recyclability of critical components and the plastics from which they are composed, allows for the definition of ecodesign measures aimed at facilitating disassembly and improving material recyclability.

2.3.5. Analysis of the Recyclability of Parts

Considering the factors presented in the previous section, several variables were taken into account to calculate the recyclability (R) of the parts, including different categories, such as the number of main polymers and subcomponents, compatibility between polymers and with additives or fillers, the presence of coatings and adhesives, and the availability of industrial-scale recycling technologies. Based on these factors, a scale was developed to systematically quantify the recyclability of the parts (see Table 6). The boundary values used in the scale (e.g., ≥ 8 and ≤ 3 for the number of main polymers) were selected based on empirical observations of typical polymer and subcomponent distributions in automotive parts. Then, recyclability values ranging from 0 to 5 were assigned to each category. The scale is arbitrary and was defined after empirical attempts to compare the

resulting scores for different components, with the main objective of quantifying qualitative characteristics influencing recyclability and enabling a comparative assessment of vehicle parts. These boundary values ensure that the scoring differentiates meaningfully between parts with high material complexity and those with simpler compositions, allowing for a consistent and comparative evaluation of recyclability across different vehicle components. This procedure is not based on an absolute criterion, but on common practice and empirical considerations.

Table 6. Scale for Quantifying Part Recyclability [37].

Indicator	Description	Score					
		0	1	2	3	4	5
A	Number of main polymers: polymeric materials present in quantities higher than 1 g are identified [10%]	≥8	7	6	5	4	≤3
B	Number of main subcomponents: only subcomponents containing polymers are considered [10%]	≥16	13–15	10–12	7–9	4–6	≤3
C	Compatibility of polymers in recycling: mean value based on the main polymer compatibility with each of the others [10%]	If not compatible	—	2.5 If limited compatibility for moderate quantities	—	If 100% compatible	
D	Compatibility of additives and fillers in recycling: mean value based on the main polymer compatibility with their additives [10%]	Prohibited additive	>60% wg	40–60% wg	20–40% wg	≤20% wg	No additives
E	Presence of coatings: paint and skin can be present and should be chemically removed [10%]	Prohibited coatings	On the main polymer (main part)	On the main polymer (secondary parts)	On the other polymers (main part)	On the other polymers (secondary parts)	No coatings
F	Presence of adhesives: adhesives in high quantities can hinder the recycling [10%]	Prohibited adhesives	On the main polymer (main part)	On the main polymer (secondary parts)	On the other polymers (main part)	On the other polymers (secondary parts)	No adhesives
G	Presence of recycling technologies for the main polymer for the same application (closed loop) [30%]	None	—	2.5 if technologies are slightly developed	—	Well-developed technologies	

The overall recyclability value is calculated by summing the weighted values of the different variables, as shown in Equation (2).

$$R = \alpha \cdot A + \beta \cdot B + \gamma \cdot C + \delta \cdot D + \varepsilon \cdot E + \epsilon \cdot F + \theta \cdot G \tag{2}$$

The weighting coefficients shown in Supplementary Materials, Table S2, reflect the relative influence of each variable on the recyclability of the part.

Factors such as the number of polymers used (A), the number of plastic-containing subparts (B), polymer compatibility (C), the use of coatings (E), and the use of adhesives (F), as defined in Table 6, are considered to have a more secondary or superficial influence on recyclability and are therefore assigned the lowest weighting coefficients of 0.1. Variables related to additives and fillers within the polymer composition (D) are given an intermediate weighting of 0.2, as they directly influence the quality and feasibility of the recycling process. Finally, recycling technologies (G) are assigned the highest weighting coefficient (0.3), since the absence of an appropriate recycling technology prevents recycling regardless of the fulfillment of all other conditions.

Recycling technologies are assigned the highest value (0.3); since appropriate recycling technology is not available, the part cannot be recycled even if all other conditions are met. Additives that are part of the polymer composition are assigned a value of 0.2, as they directly affect the recyclability of the part. Coatings and adhesives, considered “superficial,” receive a lower weight (0.1) in the calculation.

2.3.6. Ecodesign Measures

After analyzing the composition, disassemblability, and recyclability of the most critical plastic parts, three types of ecodesign measures were proposed to mitigate environmental impact: Type 1, substitution of selected plastics with lower-exergy alternatives; Type 2, incorporation of recycled plastics; and Type 3, reuse of parts in new vehicles.

Ecodesign Measure Type 1: Substitution of Plastics with Lower Exergy Materials

This measure proposes replacing high-exergy polymers such as SBR ($73.0 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$), ABS ($69.8 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$), PA ($59.3 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$), and EPDM ($55.9 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) with alternatives of lower embodied exergy, when polymers with comparable mechanical and thermal properties can be used interchangeably while maintaining performance. Based on comparative analysis of mechanical and thermal properties, we propose, for instance, that ABS can be substituted by polypropylene (PP), reducing embodied exergy while preserving functionality. This substitution strategy can contribute to environmental benefits and supports circular economy approaches. Further details can be found in Table 7.

Table 7. Proposed substitutions of polymers for the studied models.

Measure	Properties	Replacement	SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV ^a	SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV ^b	SEAT Leon Gen. II ^a	SEAT Leon Gen. II ^b	SEAT Leon Gen. III ^a	SEAT Leon Gen. III ^b
Replacement of SBR in the floor covering	Resistance to wear and abrasion; Flexibility and durability; Chemical resistance; Acoustic and thermal insulation; Resistance to water and moisture.	PVC ¹	X	X	X	X	X	X
Replacement of ABS in the door panel storage compartment	Durable and resistant to light impacts, to withstand occasional shocks; Resistant to heat and UV radiation; Aesthetically appealing, with a good finish; Easy to mold.	PP					X	X
Replacement of EPDM in the engine compartment insulator	Heat and aging resistance; Flexibility across a wide temperature range; Resistance to water, chemicals, and ozone; Reasonable acoustic damping capacity.	PU			X	X		
Replacement of ABS in the front bumper	Mechanical strength; Ease of molding; Resistance to heat and UV radiation.	PP	X	X	X	X		

Table 7. Cont.

Measure	Properties	Replacement	SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV ^a	SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV ^b	SEAT Leon Gen. II ^a	SEAT Leon Gen. II ^b	SEAT Leon Gen. III ^a	SEAT Leon Gen. III ^b
Replacement of PA in the fuel tank	Resistance to fuels and their vapors; High chemical resistance (without degradation); Resistance to heat and low temperatures; Ability to withstand impacts and deformations without cracking.	PP	X	X	X	X	X	X

¹ Possible alternative to SBR in floor covering; however, PVC is difficult to recycle and contains additives (plasticizers, thermal stabilizers) that may negatively impact human health and the environment. ^a Reference trims. ^b Formula Racing trims.

The substitution of SBR with PVC in the floor covering is considered here solely as a potential technical alternative based on material compatibility and functional requirements. However, PVC presents significant environmental and end-of-life management challenges. In particular, its recycling is complex due to its chlorine content and the presence of various additives, which may pose risks to human health and the environment [53,54]. Therefore, PVC is not proposed as a sustainable option but included to illustrate a functional substitution while explicitly acknowledging its limitations. Alternative polymeric materials with lower environmental impact, such as thermoplastic elastomers (TPE) or ethylene-vinyl acetate (EVA), may also be considered [55,56].

The reduction in embodied exergy achieved by substituting plastics with alternatives of lower exergy is calculated below. Under Type 1 measures, embodied exergy is determined using Equation (1), replacing the values of the original plastics with those of the substitute polymer. For instance, in all vehicle models, the embodied exergy of ABS in the front bumper is set to zero relative to the base case and replaced by that of PP, the designated substitute. The densities of each plastic, which vary across polymer types and influence both mass and embodied exergy, were obtained from the data sources reported in Supplementary Materials Table S3.

The savings of embodied exergy in plastics ($EE_{Savings}$) is calculated according to Equation (3):

$$EE_{Savings} = (EE_{Base Case} - EE_{Type 1}) \cdot K_{\rho i} \tag{3}$$

where $EE_{Base Case}$ represents the embodied exergy of plastics, $EE_{Type 1}$ represents the embodied exergy after implementing Type 1 measures, and $K_{\rho i}$ is the density coefficient between the plastic being replaced and its substitute. Finally, the improvement relative to the base case is obtained using Equation (4):

$$E_{improvement} (\%) = \frac{EE_{Saving}}{EE_{Base Case}} \cdot 100 \tag{4}$$

Ecodesign Measure Type 2: Substitution of Primary-Production Plastics with Recycled Materials

This measure involves replacing primary-production plastics with recycled alternatives. The exergy of recycling processes for the analyzed plastics has been obtained from ref. [37] to evaluate savings compared to manufacturing from fossil-based materials. This approach is applied to all critical parts and relevant models, aiming to reduce resource consumption while maintaining technical performance. The exergy values for the recycling of each plastic are presented in Table 8.

Table 8. Exergy of recycling processes, maximum substitution ratio, and most common recycling type of the selected plastics.

Plastic	Embodied Exergy, From Recycling (MJ·kg ⁻¹)	Maximum Replacement Rate	Source	Type of Recycling
PE	3	30%	[57]	Mechanical
PP	3	100%	[58,59]	Mechanical
PA	10	25%	[49]	Mechanical
PU	5	50%	[60–62]	Chemical (solvent-free)
EPDM	11	80%	[63–65]	Mechanical and chemical
PET	4	85%	[66]	Thermo-mechanical
ABS	2	50%	[67]	Mechanical (hot)
PC	3	90%	[68,69]	Mechanical
PVC	1	90%	[70]	Mechanical
SBR	11	10%	[38]	Chemical

The exergy required to recycle plastics is lower than that associated with producing them from virgin resources. Taking advantage of this property, the exergy savings achieved by replacing primary plastics with recycled ones can be calculated. It was assumed that the amount of plastic replaced corresponds to the maximum allowable rate ($r_{max,i}$) obtained from the literature and collected in Table 9. Accordingly, the exergy savings ($EE_{Saving,i}$) for each plastic in a part is obtained using Equation (5):

$$EE_{Saving,i} = m_i * (EE_i - E_{rec,i}) * r_{max,i} \quad (5)$$

where m_i is the mass of each plastic and $E_{rec,i}$ is the exergy needed to obtain the same plastic from secondary sources through recycling.

Table 9. Embodied Exergy Savings (%). Type 2 Measures on Studied Components.

Part	SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV ^a	SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV ^b	SEAT Leon Gen. II ^a	SEAT Leon Gen. II ^b	SEAT Leon Gen. III ^a	SEAT Leon Gen. III ^b
Front bumper	27	62	66	7	74	80
Rear bumper	2	86	2	2	72	67
Fuel tank	26	26	31	26	26	26
Floor covering	43	69	73	72	73	73
Engine compartment	-	-	59	59	43	43
insulator						
Door panel storage	-	-	-	-	38	38
compartment						

^a Reference trims. ^b Formula Racing trims.

The exergy savings for a part, j , is calculated by summing the exergy savings obtained from replacing each plastic with a recycled one (Equation (6)):

$$EE_{savings} = \sum_j EE_{savings,j} \quad (6)$$

Finally, the percentage improvement for Type 2 measures is calculated using Equation (4).

Ecodesign Measure Type 3: Reusability of Parts in New Models

These measures aim to extend the service life of vehicle parts by promoting their reuse in new models, which in practice improves recyclability through optimized disassembly and enhanced polymer compatibility. The methodology considers the type of part, its exposure to wear, and ease of disassembly to conduct a qualitative evaluation of reuse potential.

Based on average disassembly time, component accessibility, and the type of tools required, four categories of reusability are established, ranging from A (high) to D (very low):

Category A (high reusability): These parts can be disassembled in less than 20 min and are very likely to be reused. They are easily accessible and require only basic tools such as screwdrivers and common wrenches.

Category B (moderate reusability): Disassembly takes 20–40 min, with intermediate effort and slightly more steps. Tools such as levers or other common hand tools are needed.

Category C (low reusability): These parts require 40–60 min to disassemble, are harder to access, and often connected with multiple fasteners. Specialized tools, including electric or specific equipment, are needed.

Category D (very low or negligible reusability): Disassembly takes over 60 min, and parts are complex, poorly accessible, and slow to remove. Advanced specialized tools or heavy machinery are required.

In the final step of the methodology, an exergy analysis is performed to evaluate the proposed improvements relative to the baseline scenario. This case, presented in Table S4 in Supplementary Materials, represents the initial situation of the parts identified as most critical. Using their composition and the exergy of the plastics they contain, the exergy of each component is quantified. Based on this information and considering the impact of the proposed ecodesign measures, the improved scenario resulting from their implementation is calculated.

3. Results and Discussion

This section presents the results obtained from the implementation of the eco-design measures proposed in this study. These measures aim to optimize vehicle design and minimize the environmental and energetic impacts of components through strategies such as the selection of more sustainable materials, enhanced recyclability, and the reduction in embodied exergy. The subsequent subsections detail the specific results for each category of measure.

3.1. Ecodesign Measure Type 1: Substitution of Plastics with Lower Exergy Materials

The analysis of Type 1 eco-design measures reveals the potential for significant reductions in embodied exergy across the different vehicle models studied. Figure 2 shows the savings obtained (MJ) when high-exergy plastics are replaced with alternatives of lower embodied exergy, thereby decreasing the overall exergy impact of the plastic materials used in automobiles.

Figure 2. Embodied exergy savings (MJ) for the vehicle models studied after applying Type 1 measures. ^a Reference trims, ^b Formula Racing trims.

The results indicate that embodied exergy savings increase progressively from the SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV to SEAT Leon Gen. III models, suggesting that more recent vehicles offer greater potential for improving recycling and optimizing the use of plastics. Both SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV models exhibit the lowest savings, below 20 MJ, due to the absence of EPDM in the engine compartment insulator and ABS in the door panel storage compartments. In these vehicles, the part contributing most to the savings is the floor covering, although its impact is relatively limited.

The components that contribute most to embodied exergy savings vary by vehicle model. In the SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV models, the floor covering is the main contributor, and replacing SBR with PVC in this component results in savings of approximately 8 MJ for the SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV Reference and 16 MJ for the SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV Formula Racing. These results are consistent with those reported in, where the floor covering was also identified as one of the components with the highest embodied exergy due to the presence of polymers with high embodied exergy values, such as PET and SBR.

In contrast, both SEAT Leon Gen. II and SEAT Leon Gen. III models include EPDM in the engine compartment insulator, and its replacement with PU increases the embodied exergy savings compared to the previous case, exceeding 40 MJ. In these models, the door panel storage compartment also represents a major source of savings, as substituting ABS with PP results in reductions above 70 MJ. Furthermore, the floor covering continues to contribute to the overall savings, although to a lesser extent than the engine compartment insulation. This effect is so significant that, even without improvements to the engine compartment insulation. The SEAT Leon Gen. III models stand out in terms of embodied exergy efficiency, with the Reference and Formula Racing versions exhibiting very similar values across all cases. These findings are consistent with the observations reported in [46], where heavier or multi-material components exhibited higher total embodied exergy values.

The SEAT Leon Gen. III models exhibit the highest savings, approaching 70 MJ, due to the replacement of ABS with PP in the door panel storage compartments, which becomes the main part contributing to the savings. This effect is so significant that, even without improvements to the soundproofing, the SEAT Leon Gen. III models stand out in terms of

energy efficiency, with the Reference and Formula Racing versions showing very similar values in all cases.

This effect is significant enough for the SEAT Leon Gen. III models to stand out in terms of energy efficiency even without soundproofing improvements, with the Reference and Formula Racing versions showing similar values across all cases.

The results reveal a consistent shift in the distribution of embodied exergy savings across vehicle generations, where newer models concentrate savings in fewer but more influential components, particularly interior polymer-based parts. This indicates that improvements in design and material selection do not affect all components uniformly, but rather amplify the role of specific high-impact parts in determining the total savings potential. This trend is consistent with findings in the recent literature on automotive materials [71], which describe a progressive shift toward vehicle lightweighting strategies aimed at reducing mass and improving efficiency. In this context, recent reviews on automotive plastics [13] indicate an increasing role of polymeric materials in non-structural applications, particularly in interior systems such as door panels, trims, and dashboards, as well as selected exterior components such as bumpers. This reflects a broader tendency toward functional integration and part consolidation in modern vehicle design, where plastics enable complex, multi-functional components in reduced space.

Regarding alternative production routes, bio-based polymers such as PLA and PHA have been widely discussed in the literature as potential alternatives to fossil-based plastics. They are typically produced from renewable feedstocks via fermentation followed by polymerization and purification, which involve energy-intensive steps [72,73]. Several life cycle assessment studies highlight that these processes involve energy-intensive stages, particularly biomass pretreatment, fermentation, enzymatic hydrolysis, and polymer recovery. For PLA and PHA (polylactic acid and polyhydroxyalkanoates), lactic acid production through fermentation and subsequent polymerization are key contributors to energy demand [74].

From the perspective of the present study, these alternative materials would directly affect the embodied exergy of the identified vehicle components, since exergy hotspots are primarily driven by material production processes. Substituting fossil-based polymers with bio-based alternatives would modify the material-level exergy intensity, although the direction and magnitude of this change depend on the specific production pathway considered. Within the proposed framework, this is interpreted as an extension of Type 1 strategies (material substitution), whose effectiveness depends on the exergy intensity of the replaced polymer.

Recent exergy-based and life cycle assessment studies show that the highest exergy consumption in petrochemical polymers occurs in the upstream stages, specifically crude oil refining, naphtha steam cracking, and intermediate monomer synthesis, while polymerization contributes comparatively less to the total exergy demand [46]. This is in agreement with LCA evidence showing that steam cracking is the main energy-intensive step in the production of key monomers such as ethylene, which directly determines the energy burden of polymers such as PE and, by extension, PP [75].

This directly affects the interpretation of the present results, since the identified high-exergy vehicle components (e.g., seat foams, bumpers, and interior polymer-based parts) are largely driven by these upstream material production stages. Consequently, the exergy hotspots observed in the studied vehicles can be traced back to the high exergy intensity of conventional polymer production, which also explains why Type 1 strategies (substitution of high-exergy plastics) yield only moderate savings, whereas Type 2 strategies (use of recycled plastics) achieve substantially higher reductions by bypassing these upstream processes. This reinforces the component-level findings of this study, where material selection and recyclability govern the effectiveness of circularity strategies.

This trend is consistent across the polymers analyzed in this work, where more complex structures (e.g., PET, ABS, PA6.6, PU) exhibit higher embodied exergy due to multi-step synthesis routes involving additional chemical transformations and intermediates. In contrast, simpler polyolefins such as PP and PE show lower exergy requirements due to more direct conversion pathways from ethylene and propylene with fewer processing stages, which aligns with the lower embodied exergy observed in simplified polymer chains in our component-level analysis.

3.2. Ecodesign Measure Type 2: Substitution of Primary-Production Plastics with Recycled Plastics

With regard to the Type 2 measures, Figure 3 shows the embodied exergy savings achieved by substituting primary plastics with recycled ones for each vehicle model. In this figure, bars illustrate the absolute savings broken down by part, and the right axis is represented by an orange line indicating the relative savings with respect to the baseline case. The highest absolute saving corresponds to SEAT Leon Gen. II Reference, with almost 1.7 GJ, followed by both SEAT Leon Gen. III and SEAT Leon Gen. II Formula Racing models, with about 1.4 GJ. In relative terms, SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV Formula Racing, SEAT Leon Gen. II Reference and SEAT Leon Gen. III series achieve savings between 50% and 55%, whereas in SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV Reference and SEAT Leon Gen. II Reference models the savings are below 40% and 45%, respectively.

In this context, Type 2 measures, enable significant exergy savings: in the SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV Reference model, the savings reach 37%, while in the other models they range from 45 to 53%. Similar ranges have been reported in recent polymer recycling studies, where the substitution of virgin PP or PET with recycled polymers led to exergy or energy reductions of 40–55% [13,46].

In most models, the front bumper represents the component with the greatest potential for embodied exergy savings through the use of recycled materials, due to its high content of substitutable plastics such as ethylene, polycarbonate, and particularly polypropylene. In SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV Reference and SEAT Leon Gen. II Formula Racing models, the lower polypropylene content limits this potential: in the SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV Reference, over 40% of the mass consists of polyethylene, while in the SEAT Leon Gen. II Formula Racing model, nearly 90% is composed of E/P copolymer. This copolymer is produced by polymerizing ethylene and propylene in variable proportions, and although research is underway to enable partial recovery, knowledge of the exact monomer ratio is essential [76].

Therefore, it is recommended that front bumpers be primarily manufactured from polypropylene, and that in cases where E/P copolymer is used, the ethylene-to-propylene ratio be specified to facilitate replacement with recycled material. Similarly, the rear bumper represents a significant exergy requirement across all models. In the SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV Reference and SEAT Leon Gen. II models, the potential savings are limited (Table 9), mainly due to the use of E/P copolymer.

However, the feasibility of increasing recycled content in these components is constrained by functional requirements. From a functional perspective, bumpers are components that must comply with mechanical performance requirements under impact conditions; therefore, the incorporation of recycled polymers must ensure that material properties are not adversely affected [77]. In addition, environmental aging mechanisms such as long-term exposure to UV radiation, temperature fluctuations, and thermo-oxidative degradation can contribute to polymer property deterioration, which may limit the allowable fraction of recycled material unless stabilization strategies are applied [13].

In contrast, interior components such as dashboards and floor covering systems (e.g., carpets) are generally not primary structural components and therefore tend to present greater flexibility for recycled polymer integration. Although they remain subject to

in-service thermal and environmental aging within the vehicle cabin, their functional requirements are typically less stringent in terms of mechanical loading, which can make them more suitable candidates for higher recycled content integration.

Figure 3. Embodied exergy savings (MJ) in the studied car models after applying Type 2 measures. Bars show the absolute savings broken down by component (left axis), while the line represents the relative savings in percentage (right axis). ^a Reference trims, ^b Formula Racing trims.

Within this context, the differences in recycling potential among bumper components are directly governed by polymer composition, with higher polypropylene content enabling greater applicability of recycled material substitution, whereas the presence of E/P copolymers introduces a key limitation due to their variable and less well-defined composition.

By contrast, the other three models contain a higher proportion of polypropylene in the rear bumper, enabling greater substitution with recycled material. Accordingly, it is recommended to increase the PP content in rear bumpers or, alternatively, to specify the composition of the E/P copolymer to enhance the potential for substitution.

Another component with significant potential for embodied exergy savings through the use of recycled material is the floor covering. Its high embodied exergy is mainly due to its PET content. This plastic, widely used in packaging, exhibits a high recycling and

substitution rate. In the SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV Reference model, the use of PE instead of PET results in lower substitution with recycled material and therefore lower embodied exergy savings. It is recommended that the SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV Reference adopt a floor covering similar to that used in the other models.

For the engine compartment insulator, a marked difference is observed between the SEAT Leon Gen. II and III and models. The SEAT Leon Gen. II models contain a higher proportion of EPDM, which enables greater substitution potential and thus higher exergy savings. In the SEAT Leon Gen. III models, the larger mass of polyurethane reduces this substitution potential. Nevertheless, this effect is partially offset because PU has a lower embodied exergy than EPDM. Additionally, the SEAT Leon Gen. III models include 1.2 g of unspecified plastics. It is therefore recommended that, in the SEAT Leon Gen. III models, the plastics composing this part be specified or that the same composition as in the SEAT Leon Gen. II models be adopted.

A similar situation is observed for the front section. In the SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV Reference model, this component is made of an unspecified plastic, preventing consideration of recycled material incorporation. By contrast, in the SEAT Leon Gen. II and SEAT Leon Gen. III models, the use of polypropylene allows for significant embodied exergy savings when primary plastic is replaced by recycled polypropylene. Accordingly, it is recommended that the SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV Reference specify the type of plastic used in this part, or alternatively adopt the polypropylene composition employed in the SEAT Leon Gen. II and SEAT Leon Gen. III models.

Using recycled plastics also reduces differences between models; without recycled plastics, the exergy difference between the SEAT Leon Gen. II and SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV models reaches almost 2000 MJ, while with recycled plastics it is reduced to 1000 MJ. This homogenization trend aligns with broader circular design research showing that material recirculation narrows the sustainability gap between vehicle classes by reducing dependency on fossil feedstocks [11]. Within this context, certain plastics stand out for their higher potential for exergy savings when recycled: PP, EPDM, PET, and PC, due to their high substitution rates and associated exergy differences. Previous studies highlight that replacing polymers such as PP and PET with recycled grades offers significant life cycle benefits, as these materials account for the largest share of automotive plastic mass [78,79].

Although new processes enable more efficient recycling of PVC, this polymer is still discouraged by the automotive industry. Nevertheless, including or excluding PVC does not significantly impact overall exergy savings, as it is present in only two components among the SEAT Leon Gen. III models. This approach is consistent with current strategies by original equipment manufacturers to remove PVC in favor of more easily recyclable thermoplastics, as noted by Baldassarre et al. [80].

3.3. Comparison of Type 1 and Type 2 Results

This section focuses on the analysis of embodied exergy in vehicles. Embodied exergy reflects the total exergy required throughout the vehicle life cycle and is used to assess the exergy demand of critical components, providing insights for improving energy efficiency and reducing environmental impact and production and operating costs. As shown in Figure 4, the embodied exergy (in MJ) required for the production of plastics in these components across six vehicle configurations, differentiated by model and version (Reference and Formula Racing), allows a clear visualization of the impact of the strategies implemented.

Figure 4. Comparison of embodied exergy (MJ) in critical components of the vehicle models for the base case (no recycling) and for Type 1 and Type 2 measures. ^a Reference trims, ^b Formula Racing trims.

The comparison of the base case with the evaluated recycling scenarios confirms that Type 1 recycling allows a moderate reduction in embodied exergy in the manufacturing processes of the studied models, although with variations depending on the vehicle model. Consistent with findings by Liu et al. [81], mechanical recycling yields moderate gains, while advanced or chemical recycling routes could achieve higher systemic benefits in future developments.

In contrast, Type 2 recycling proves to be the most efficient option for improving sustainability in the automotive sector, achieving a significant decrease in embodied exergy in all cases. These results highlight the importance of implementing advanced recycling strategies to reduce exergy impact and promote lower dependence on fossil-based materials in the automotive industry. Therefore, this study reinforces recent circular economy approaches in mobility [82], confirming that high substitution rates of recycled polymers significantly improve the efficiency of material and energy use in vehicles. This higher performance of Type 2 recycling is consistently reflected across all vehicle models, indicating that its greater effectiveness is largely independent of vehicle configuration.

In a broader context of circular economy and material sustainability, these findings can be complemented by recent advances in plastic recycling. Current progress in this field focuses on improvements in three main areas: advanced mechanical recycling, chemical recycling, and emerging separation and conversion technologies. In this study, based on [83], it is highlighted that mechanical recycling remains the dominant technology, but it has significantly improved thanks to advanced sorting systems (e.g., optical sensors and AI-based algorithms) and compatibilization techniques that enable the production of higher-quality and purer recycled materials.

In parallel, chemical recycling has seen important progress, allowing polymers to be broken down into monomers or raw materials through processes such as depolymerization, pyrolysis, or selective dissolution. This makes it possible to treat mixed or contaminated waste that is not suitable for mechanical recycling. A concrete example in this study is PET depolymerization, where recent catalytic processes can recover monomers at high yields (up to ~85%), enabling their reuse in applications equivalent to virgin materials. Another relevant example is the use of AI-based sorting systems, which can reach accuracies of around 95% in plastic separation, significantly improving the quality of the recycled stream.

In a theoretical scenario of 100% recycled plastic use, embodied exergy would be significantly reduced by avoiding primary production stages; however, technical limitations such as material degradation and performance requirements still prevent full substitution in many applications. From an implementation perspective, Type 2 measures are generally

more straightforward and cost-effective than Type 1, as they do not require major redesign or requalification processes, making them more feasible for short-term industrial adoption.

As an example, for the front bumper of the SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV in Reference trim, the exergy saving obtained in this study for the considered component is 48.72 MJ. This value corresponds to the exergy reduction associated with using recycled plastic instead of conventional plastic. In a 100% recycled plastic scenario, the total saving is obtained by multiplying this value by the mass of the component (7.3 kg), resulting in a total exergy saving of approximately 355.66 MJ, compared to full production using conventional materials.

Overall, this study shows a transition from traditional approaches toward more sophisticated recycling systems that improve material quality and expand industrial applicability, although challenges related to cost, energy consumption, and scalability still remain.

The embodied exergy in the plastics of critical components increases from model SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV to model SEAT Leon Gen. III, as larger and more highly equipped vehicles require greater amounts of plastics with higher exergy impacts. In the SEAT Leon Gen. III Reference model, the embodied exergy amounts to 840 MJ in the baseline case, 710 MJ when applying the Type 1 measure, and 400 MJ with Type 2 recycling. The implementation of Type 1 measures slightly reduces embodied exergy, with variations depending on the vehicle model, whereas Type 2 recycling achieves a substantially greater reduction, demonstrating higher efficiency and a lower dependence on fossil-based materials. Finally, the differences between the Reference and Formula Racing versions are minimal across all scenarios, indicating that material composition has little influence on embodied exergy and that both strategies are similarly effective.

At the component level, when only critical components are considered, the savings from Type 2 measures greatly exceed those of Type 1 measures. In addition to critical components, the front and rear bumper are also parts where substantial exergy can be saved. Similar hotspots have been identified in component-level analyses, where bumpers, dashboards, and interior trim were highlighted as the most promising parts for recycled plastic integration due to their high mass and suitability for recycled materials [84,85]. These results further indicate that the most relevant contributions to exergy reduction are concentrated in a limited set of high-mass and high-plastic-content parts, particularly bumpers and interior components, which consistently dominate the savings potential across recycling scenarios.

From an industrial perspective, these findings suggest that efforts to reduce embodied exergy should be focused on a limited number of high-impact components rather than applied uniformly across the vehicle. This enables manufacturers to prioritize design-for-recycling strategies, material substitution, and supplier engagement specifically for bumpers and interior parts, where the return in terms of exergy savings is greatest. Such targeted measures may improve cost-effectiveness, reduce redesign and qualification efforts, and facilitate the integration of recycled plastics into existing production systems, while still meeting performance requirements.

3.4. Disassembly and Reusability of Vehicle Parts in New Models

The reuse of components in new vehicle models constitutes a key strategy to optimize material use and reduce environmental impact. To assess its feasibility, a qualitative analysis is carried out, taking into account the type of component, its level of wear exposure, and ease of disassembly. In this way, components that exhibit low degradation during use and can be disassembled without compromising their integrity show a higher potential for reuse, thereby contributing to both resource efficiency and waste reduction in the sector. To assess component reusability, four qualitative categories are proposed, ranging from A

(high) to D (very low). These categories are described in Section 2.3.6, “Ecodesign Measure Type 3—Reusability of Parts in New Models”.

For Type 3 measures, the ease of extraction directly influences the reuse of components: those that are easier to disassemble have a higher likelihood of being repurposed, as they incur less damage and require only simple tools, whereas components that are more difficult to extract present a higher risk of deterioration and lower reuse feasibility.

Table 10 shows the disassembly times, accessibility (rated as Easy, Moderate, Difficult, or Very Difficult), required tools, and reusability levels for the studied vehicle models, highlighting how design and assembly features affect their potential for reuse. The columns corresponding to each vehicle model and the “Average” column report the disassembly times, measured in minutes.

Table 10. Disassembly times measured in minutes and reusability characteristics of the studied vehicle models.

Parts	SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV ^a	SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV ^b	SEAT Leon Gen. II ^a	SEAT Leon Gen. II ^b	SEAT Leon Gen. III ^a	SEAT Leon Gen. III ^b	Average Time	Reusability Level	Accessibility Difficulty	Required Tools
Front seat backrest foam (left)	42	42	30	30	48	48	40	B	Moderate	Semi-specialized
Front seat backrest foam (right)	42	42	30	30	48	48	40	B	Moderate	Semi-specialized
Rear seat foam (cushion)	12	12	9	9	24	24	15	A	Easy	Basic
Rear seat backrest foam (left)	21	21	21	21	21	21	21	B	Moderate	Semi-specialized
Rear seat backrest foam (right)	21	21	33	33	30	30	28	B	Moderate	Semi-specialized
Front end module	60	60	75	75	90	90	75	D	Very difficult	Advanced specialized
Front window guide (left)	33	33	42	42	27	27	34	B	Moderate	Semi-specialized
Front window guide (right)	39	39	42	42	27	27	36	B	Moderate	Semi-specialized
Dashboard insulator	24	24	15	15	15	15	18	A	Easy	Basic
Front bumper	36	36	42	42	57	57	45	C	Difficult	Specialized
Rear bumper	27	27	30	30	27	27	28	B	Moderate	Semi-specialized
Fuel tank	99	99	69	69	69	69	79	D	Very difficult	Advanced specialized
Floor covering	57	57	75	75	60	60	64	D	Very difficult	Advanced specialized
Dashboard	84	84	99	99	81	81	88	D	Very difficult	Advanced specialized
Front door panel (left)	27	27	48	48	18	18	31	B	Moderate	Semi-specialized
Front door panel (right)	27	27	48	48	18	18	31	B	Moderate	Semi-specialized
Rear door panel (left)	27	27	33	33	18	18	26	B	Moderate	Semi-specialized
Rear door panel (right)	27	27	33	33	18	18	26	B	Moderate	Semi-specialized

^a Reference trims. ^b Formula Racing trims.

Among the components analyzed, the average disassembly times range from 15 to 88 min. The components with the shortest and longest disassembly times are the rear seat cushion and the dashboard, respectively. Assuming a normal distribution of the values, it can be stated that in 68.3% of the cases (mean value ± standard deviation), the disassembly

times fall between 18 and 61 min. This highlights the high dispersion of the values around the mean disassembly time (40 min).

When analyzing the results by component, it is observed that, regardless of the vehicle model, components exhibit similar disassembly times. For example, the rear seat cushion and door panels are quick to disassemble in all cases, whereas the dashboard and fuel tanks are among the most complex components. This is expected given their location and size. Considering the mean disassembly time (40 min), the front bumper, floor covering, front-end module, fuel tank, and dashboard exceed this value. It is noteworthy that only one component has a disassembly time equal to or less than 15 min (rear seat cushion). Even in the case of panels or external components (e.g., bumpers), disassembly requires significant labor, which constitutes a major barrier to enhancing recyclability. Nevertheless, it should be noted that the reported disassembly times correspond to careful disassembly procedures, without damaging any fastening or joining systems.

The level of component reuse shown in the previous table varies depending on the ease of extraction and the condition of the components after disassembly. Based on the results, it is observed that some components exhibit a high reuse potential (A), such as the rear seat cushion padding and the dashboard sound insulation. These components stand out because their disassembly is straightforward, requiring basic or moderately specialized tools, and they do not suffer significant damage during the process.

On the other hand, several components show a medium reuse potential (B), including the front and rear seatback padding, front windshield guides, rear bumper, and door panels. Although the extraction of these components is feasible, it involves intermediate access difficulty and the use of specific tools. As a result, their reuse is possible, but not always guaranteed.

Components with a low reuse potential (C), such as the front bumper, present more complex disassembly procedures, which may lead to damage to the component and consequently reduce the likelihood of successful reuse. In these cases, the feasibility of reuse strongly depends on the care taken during extraction and the final condition of the component.

Finally, some components exhibit a very low or negligible reuse potential (D), such as the front-end module, fuel tank, floor covering, and dashboard. These components require long disassembly times, access is highly restricted, and advanced specialized tools are necessary. In addition, the risk of damage during extraction is high, rendering their reuse unfeasible in many cases.

3.5. Recyclability of Parts

Considering the values of the indicators A to G presented in Table 7 of Section 2.3.5, “Analysis of the Recyclability of Parts”, as well as Equation (2), the recyclability value (R) has been calculated for each analyzed part (see Table 11).

At present, several components—specifically the rear seats, the floor covering, and the front-end module—lack industrial-scale recycling processes. Rear seats are mainly composed of PU foam combined with textile covers made of PES, PET, and PAN fibers; floor coverings are primarily manufactured from PET and PP fibers; and the front-end module is produced from PP with a high content of glass fibers (GFs). In all these cases, the high fiber content significantly hinders recyclability, as suitable industrial recycling technologies for these material combinations are not yet available.

Table 11. Overview of the recyclability of the analyzed parts.

	Front Seat Backrest Foam	Front Window Guide	Rear Bumper	Dashboard	Front Door Panel	Fuel Tank	Asientos Traseros	Floor Covering	Front-End Module
A: Number of polymers (m > 1 g)	5	5	2	0	0	0	3	1	5
B: Number of subparts containing plastic materials	4	3	1	0	3	0	5	4	5
C: Compatibility of polymers in recycling processes	5	5	1.7	2	0	0	0	0	0
D: Compatibility of adhesives and fillers in recycling	4	2	4.5	2.5	4	4	4	4.7	3
E: Use of coatings	4	4	1.5	5	1	3	2	1	1
F: Use of adhesives	5	4	4	3	2	3	2	4	1
G: Availability of recycling technologies	2.5	2.5	3.8	3.1	2.5	2.5	0	0	0
Total score	3.9 ¹	3.3	3	2.4	2.2	2.2	2	1.9	1.8

¹ The reported value refers exclusively to the seat foam material. Recyclability of complete seat assemblies is significantly lower due to their multi-material composition (e.g., foam, polymer sandwich structures, and textile components).

In addition to material composition, the widespread use of additives and surface coatings, while beneficial for enhancing mechanical performance and perceived quality, further penalizes recyclability when these substances are applied directly to the main component and cannot be removed through disassembly. This limitation is evident in components such as bumpers, which use titanium dioxide (TiO₂) coatings, and door panels incorporating magnesium silicate (MgSiO₃). A similar reduction in recyclability is observed in components with a high diversity of polymers, such as the dashboard—composed of PP, PVC, PU, PET, EPM, and PE—and the fuel tank, which consists mainly of PE but includes a significant proportion of POM in seals and functional subcomponents. In these cases, limited polymer compatibility and the presence of multiple materials substantially constrain recycling efficiency.

Conversely, components with a simpler and more homogeneous material composition show significantly better recyclability. The front seat foam and the front window guide stand out as the most recyclable components, as they are composed almost entirely of a single polymer (97% PUR and 98% EPDM, respectively), which strongly favors polymer compatibility and recycling feasibility. More generally, components designed with fewer subcomponents and reduced material diversity demonstrate improved recyclability, particularly when disassembly prior to recycling is feasible.

Overall, the front-end module and the floor covering exhibit the lowest recyclability performance, primarily due to their high fiber content and the absence of developed recycling technologies for such reinforced or fiber-based materials. These findings highlight the critical importance of material selection, polymer compatibility, and design-for-disassembly strategies in improving the recyclability of automotive components.

These observations are consistent with the findings of [19], where an exergy-based classification showed that the most critical plastic components are not necessarily the heaviest ones but those made of polymers with higher exergy intensity and lower recyclability. That study also identified floor coverings, door panels, dashboards, and sound insulation as key parts for improving circularity. Moreover, it emphasized that accessibility and ease of disassembly are decisive factors for enhancing reuse and recycling, highlighting the importance of design-for-disassembly approaches to advance circularity in the automotive sector.

4. Conclusions

In this paper, the embodied exergy of plastic vehicle parts was evaluated to identify the most critical components in terms of their physical exergy value. The proposed methodology was applied to three vehicle models (SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV and SEAT Leon Gen. II and III) with two trim levels (Reference and Formula Racing), considering disassemblability and recyclability criteria. Based on this analysis, three ecodesign measures were proposed: substitution of high-exergy plastics, use of recycled materials, and component reuse. The main original contribution of this work lies in the integration of embodied exergy assessment with disassembly and recyclability criteria to establish a comparative, component-level framework for automotive plastic circularity. Importantly, the proposed methodology is not limited to specific vehicle trims or models, but is generally applicable to any passenger vehicle, enabling its use across different automotive platforms and manufacturers. From this work, the following conclusions can be drawn.

Vehicle parts with high embodied exergy, such as front and rear seat foams, require substantial exergy for production. Identifying these parts helps prioritize recycling efforts and guides material and design optimization to reduce the overall exergy demand in automotive manufacturing. This study further demonstrates how exergy-based ranking can systematically support design-for-circularity decisions at the component level.

Embodied exergy savings increase with the evolution of automobile models. This trend can be attributed to the use of lighter and more recyclable materials, improvements in manufacturing processes, a growing focus on the circular economy, and stricter environmental regulations that encourage the design of easily recyclable parts. Beyond confirming these general tendencies, the comparative multi-model analysis quantifies how design evolution translates into exergy savings at the component level across vehicle generations. However, although these advanced materials are more sustainable, their production often involves energy-intensive processes. Overall, technological innovation and optimized vehicle design are crucial to maximize the efficient use of recyclable materials and advance sustainability in the automotive sector.

The components that contribute most to embodied exergy savings vary by vehicle model. For example, in the SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV models, the floor covering is the main contributor, and replacing certain polymers, such as SBR and PET, with PVC in this component results in notable exergy savings. However, due to the environmental concerns associated with PVC, alternative polymeric materials with lower environmental impact, such as thermoplastic elastomers (TPE) or ethylene-vinyl acetate (EVA), may also be considered. This highlights the model-specific nature of exergy hotspots, which is a key outcome of the proposed methodology.

In the SEAT Leon Gen. II and SEAT Leon Gen. III models, the engine compartment insulator and the door panel storage compartment are the main contributors, highlighting that high-embodied exergy polymers can be replaced to achieve substantial savings. The identification of consistent critical components across generations strengthens the robustness of the proposed exergy-based prioritization approach.

The potential embodied exergy savings depend not only on the type of polymer but also on the functional role and mass of each component. This result reinforces the multi-factorial nature of exergy savings, which is explicitly captured in the proposed methodological framework.

Additionally, no significant differences were observed between the Reference and Formula Racing versions of the studied models, indicating that replacing plastics has a similar effect on both versions and depends more on the overall vehicle design. This finding supports the transferability and analytical consistency of the methodology across different vehicle configurations.

Type 2 measures, which involve replacing primary plastics with recycled plastics, enable significant exergy savings across all studied vehicle models, reaching up to 53%. These savings are substantially higher than those obtained through Type 1 measures, particularly when critical components are considered. In this context, the front and rear bumpers emerge as components with especially high exergy-saving potential. A key contribution of this work is the quantification and comparison of Type 1 and Type 2 strategies under a unified exergy framework, enabling direct evaluation of circularity interventions.

The use of recycled plastics reduces exergy disparities between vehicle models, contributing to a more homogeneous exergy performance across different vehicle classes. In this context, polymers with high substitution potential, such as PP, PET, EPDM, and PC, play a key role in maximizing exergy savings.

The Type 1 strategy, based on the substitution of high-exergy plastics with lower-exergy alternatives, achieves moderate reductions in embodied exergy across the studied vehicle models by acting at the raw material selection stage.

Type 2 strategy (recycling) is the most efficient approach for enhancing sustainability in the automotive sector, substantially reducing embodied exergy and promoting lower dependence on fossil-based materials. High substitution rates of recycled polymers significantly improve the efficiency of material and energy use in vehicles. This study directly relates disassembly ease to exergy savings, reinforcing the importance of design for disassembly in the analysis.

The ease of component extraction significantly affects their potential for reuse, highlighting the importance of selecting appropriate materials and implementing effective disassembly and recycling strategies to maximize exergy savings in the automotive industry. Exergy savings depend not only on material selection but also on component disassembly feasibility, reinforcing the need for integrated design strategies.

The most critical plastic components for circularity are not necessarily the heaviest, but those with high exergy intensity and low recyclability. Accessibility and ease of disassembly are key factors to enhance reuse and recycling, highlighting the importance of design-for-disassembly strategies in advancing circularity in the automotive sector. This challenges mass-based prioritization approaches and supports an exergy-driven selection criterion for circular design.

Overall, the consistency between the present results and previous studies confirms that polymer material is a key driver for reducing embodied exergy in automotive components. However, the present work develops a structured comparative methodology that enables the systematic identification and ranking of exergy-critical components across different vehicle models and design variants. This approach provides a more detailed and transferable assessment framework for supporting material substitution and recycling decisions. Material substitution and recycling strategies therefore represent effective pathways for improving the environmental performance of vehicle manufacturing.

Supplementary Materials: The following supporting information can be downloaded at: <https://www.mdpi.com/article/10.3390/recycling11050085/s1>, Table S1: Production routes of different

polymers [86–91]; Table S2: Weighting Coefficients for Recyclability Calculation Variables; Table S3: Densities of the plastics considered. Values in $\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ [92–103]; Table S4: Baseline condition of parts identified as most critical. Exergy values in MJ.

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

ABS	Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene
ACM	Acrylic Rubber
AEM	Acrylate Ethylene Monomer Rubber
ASR	Automotive Shredder Residue
E/P	Polypropylene–Ethylene Blend
ECO	Epichlorohydrin Rubber
EDC	Ethylene Dichloride
EE	Embodied Exergy (MJ)
$EE_{\text{Base case}}$	Embodied exergy of plastics for each vehicle model (MJ)
EE_i	Embodied exergy of each polymer or plastic comprising the piece (MJ)
EE_{Savings}	Embodied exergy savings in plastics (MJ)
$EE_{\text{Type 1}}$	Embodied exergy after implementing Type 1 measures (MJ)
EG	Ethylene Glycol
$E_{\text{improvement}}$	Percentage improvement relative to the base case (%)
EPDM	Ethylene Propylene Diene Monomer
EPM	Ethylene Propylene Monomer
EVOH	Ethylene-Vinyl Alcohol
FKM	Fluoroelastomer
FR	Formula Racing
HHV	Higher Heating Value $\text{MJ}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$
HMD	Hexamethylenediamine
i	Plastics or polymers composing vehicle parts
IIR	Butyl Rubber (Isobutylene Isoprene Rubber)
j	Vehicle parts, e.g., front bumper, dashboard, and other analyzed elements
KA	Ketone-Aldehyde
K_{pi}	Density coefficient between the plastic being replaced and its substitute
LED	Light-Emitting Diode
MDI	Methylene Diphenyl Diisocyanate

m_i	Mass of each polymer comprising the piece
NR	Natural Rubber
PAN	Polyacrylonitrile
PA66	Polyamide 6.6
PC	Polycarbonate
PE	Polyethylene
PET	Polyethylene Terephthalate
PES	Polyester fibers
PF	Phenolic Resin
PMMA	Polymethyl Methacrylate
POM	Polyoxymethylene (Polyacetal)
PP	Polypropylene
PPS	Polyphenylene Sulfide
PS	Polystyrene
PSU	Polysulfones
PTA	Terephthalic Acid
PU	Polyurethane
PVB	Polyvinyl Butyral
PVC	Polyvinyl Chloride
R	Overall recyclability value
REF	Reference
$r_{\max,i}$	Maximum plastic allowable rate (%)
SBR	Styrene-Butadiene Rubber
TPC-ET	Copolyester (Thermoplastic Copolyester—Ester Type)
TPS-SEBS	Thermoplastic Elastomer (Styrene—Ethylene—Butylene—Styrene)
VAG	Volkswagen Aktiengesellschaft Group
VCM	Vinyl Chloride Monomer
VMQ	Silicone Rubber
Wt	Weight percent (%)

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